

Synthesis and fungitoxicity of aldimines and 4-thiazolidinones derived from 4-bromoaniline

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Abstract : Condensation of 4-bromoaniline with benzaldehyde and substituted benzaldehydes (1-8) in equimolar ratio resulted in the formation of benzal-4-bromoaniline and its C-phenyl derivatives (1a-8a). Addition of thioglycolic acid to 1a-8a yielded the respective 4-thiazolidinone (1b-8b). The synthesized compounds were characterized on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral studies and were screened against five phytopathogenic fungi.

Keywords : Aldimines, fungitoxicity, thiazolidinone, bromoaniline.

Introduction

The synthesis and assaying of biological potential of imines and 4-thiazolidinones have received considerable interest in the recent years¹⁻⁴. The nature of the substituent^{5,6} and its position⁷ in the molecule plays a vital role in determining the chemical and biological behaviour of imines and 4-thiazolidinones. The presence of a chloro substituent in the phenyl ring of a molecule has been reported to increase the activity of the parent compound⁸. But, so far no attempt has been made to study the effect of the presence of bromo substituent in the imines and 4-thiazolidinones on their activity. This paper describes the synthesis of benzal-4-bromoanilines, their conversion into 4-thiazolidinones, their characterization on the basis of spectral studies and their fungitoxicity.

Aldimines (1a-8a) were synthesized by condensing 4-bromoaniline with benzaldehyde and substituted benzaldehydes in equimolar ratio. The crude products were recrystallized from ethanol and identified as benzal-4-bromoaniline (1a), 4-chlorobenzal-4-bromoaniline (2a), 4-hydroxybenzal-4-bromoaniline (3a), 4-methoxybenzal-4-bromoaniline (4a), 3,4-dimethoxybenzal-4-bromoaniline (5a), 3,4,5-trimethoxybenzal-4-bromoaniline (6a), 3-methoxy-4-hydroxybenzal-4-bromoaniline (7a) and 3-ethoxy-4-hydroxybenzal-4-bromoaniline (8a) on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral studies. The ultraviolet spectra taken in ethanol showed four bands, with a characteristic band between 262-275 nm indicating the presence of carbon-nitrogen double bond in the products. The IR spectra of the compounds (KBr discs) showed a characteristic band at $\sim 1625\text{ cm}^{-1}$ depicting the forma-

tion of carbon-nitrogen double bond. The chemical evidence for the formation of $>C=N-$ linkage has been supported by the complete disappearance of characteristic band in UV and IR spectra on reduction of these compounds.

In PMR spectra of the compounds in CDCl_3 , all the protons resonated in the expected field. Multiplet signals of integration corresponding to 9 protons in compound 1a, 8 protons in compounds 2a, 3a and 4a, 7 protons in compounds 5a, 7a and 8a and 6 protons in compound 6a observed between δ 6.8-7.7 were due to aromatic protons. The one proton singlet at about δ 8.3 indicated the presence of azomethenic proton in all the compounds. A singlet at δ 4.0 corresponding the three protons in compounds 4a and 7a, six protons in compound 5a and nine protons in compound 6a indicated the presence of methoxy protons in these products. A one proton singlet at about δ 9.2 in compounds 3a, 7a and 8a showed the presence of phenolic proton. The PMR spectrum of 8a contained a three proton triplet at δ 1.4 and a two proton quartet at δ 4.1 indicating the presence of an ethoxy group in the molecule.

The carbons in the products were characterized with the help of ^{13}C NMR spectra which indicated twelve aromatic carbons as eight bands between 121-152 ppm in compounds 1a-3a and between 114-162 ppm and 106-150 for the compounds 4a and 6a respectively. There are ten bands in the case of compounds 5a, 7a and 8a for aromatic carbons between 112-149 ppm. The azomethenic carbon was indicated at about 160 ppm in ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compounds. The one methoxy carbon in

the compound **4a** and **7a** was indicated at 55.8 and 56.1 ppm respectively. The ^{13}C NMR of compound of **5a** showed a single band at 56.1 and that of **6a** indicated two bands at 56.1 and 56.4 ppm respectively for two and three methoxy carbons respectively. The ethoxy carbons in compound **8a** were indicated at 64.9 and 14.8 ppm. In the mass spectra of the compounds the molecular ion peak constituted the base peak (Table 1). The aldimines of 4-bromoaniline along with their characteristics and molecular ion peak are recorded in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics and molecular ion peak of benzal-4-bromoanilines

Compd.	R	M.p. ^a (°C)	Yield (%)	M ⁺ [*] (m/z)	Molecular formula ^b
1a	H	60	85	260	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NBr
2a	4-Cl	129	88	294	C ₁₃ H ₉ NCIBr
3a	4-OH	204	90	276	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ ONBr
4a	4-OCH ₃	121	95	290	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ ONBr
5a	3-OCH ₃	112	76	320	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ NBr
	4-OCH ₃				
6a	3-OCH ₃	150	68	350	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₃ NBr
	4-OCH ₃				
	5-OCH ₃				
7a	3-OCH ₃	133	89	306	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ NBr
	4-OH				
8a	3-OC ₂ H ₅	80	73	320	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ NBr
	4-OH				

^aThe melting points are uncorrected.

^bThe compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

Addition of thioglycolic acid to benzal-4-bromoaniline and its C-phenyl derivatives (**1a-8a**) yielded the crude products **1b-8b** respectively. The crude products were crystallized from benzene and characterized as 2-phenyl-3-(4-bromophenyl)-4-thiazolidinone (**1b**), 2-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-(4-bromophenyl)-4-thiazolidinone (**2b**), 2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(4-bromophenyl)-4-thiazolidinone (**3b**), 2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-3-(4-bromophenyl)-4-thiazolidinone (**4b**), 2-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-3-(4-bromophenyl)-4-thiazolidinone (**5b**), 2-(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)-3-(4-bromophenyl)-4-thiazolidinone (**6b**), 2-(3-methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(4-bromophenyl)-4-thiazolidinone (**7b**) and 2-(3-ethoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(4-bromophenyl)-4-thiazolidinone (**8b**) with the support of elemental analysis and spectral studies. The IR spectra

of the compounds showed a band at $\sim 1690\text{ cm}^{-1}$ confirming the presence of carbonyl group in the molecules.

In PMR spectra of the compounds in CDCl₃, two methylene protons of 4-thiazolidinone ring were indicated at δ 3.9 and one proton of C-2 of the five membered ring at δ 6.0 as a singlet. A multiplet between δ 6.9–7.8 equivalent to 9 protons in compound **1b**; 8 protons in compounds **2b**, **3b** and **4b**; 7 protons in compounds **5b**, **7b** and **8b** and 6 protons in the compound **6b** was due to aromatic protons. The methoxy protons, three in compounds **4b** and **7b**, six in compound **5b** and nine in compound **6b** were indicated at $\delta \sim 4.1$ as a singlet. The phenolic proton in compounds **3b**, **7b** and **8b** was indicated as a singlet at $\delta \sim 9.3$. The ethoxy protons in compound **8b** were indicated as a three proton triplet at δ 1.4 and a two proton quartet at δ 4.00.

The carbons of 4-thiazolidinones were characterized on the basis of ^{13}C NMR spectra of the products. Twelve aromatic carbons were indicated in ^{13}C NMR of 4-thiazolidinones as eight bands between 118–140 ppm in compounds **1b** and **2b**; between 118–158 ppm in compounds **3b** and **4b**; between 106–150 ppm for compound **6b**. There were ten bands for aromatic carbons between 114–150 ppm for compounds **5b**, **7b** and **8b**. The C-2 carbon of 4-thiazolidinone ring, the methylene carbon and carbonyl carbon were indicated at ~ 60 , 33–34 and 171 ppm respectively. The one methoxy carbon in the compounds **4b** and **7b** was shown at 55.6 and 56.0 ppm respectively. Two methoxy carbons of compound **5b** and three methoxy carbons of compound **6b** were indicated as a single band (56.1 ppm) and two bands (56.1 and 56.4) respectively. The bands at 64.9 and 14.8 ppm in compound **8b** indicated the ethoxy carbons. The mass spectra of 4-thiazolidinones did not show molecular ion peak. The 4-thiazolidinones along with their characteristics are recorded in Table 2.

The aldimines (**1a-8a**) and their 4-thiazolidinones (**1b-8b**) were screened *in vitro* for their fungitoxicity against *Alternaria alternata*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Colletotrichum capsici*, *Myrothecium roridum* and *Ustilago tritici* by spore germination inhibition⁹ techniques. The results have been expressed in terms of ED₅₀ values i.e. the effective dose at which 50 per cent spore germination inhibition was caused in Table 3.

Six aldimines and five 4-thiazolidinones have been found to be quite effective against *A. alternata* showing ED₅₀ values less than 1000 ppm. 4-Thiazolidinones showed better fungitoxicity than test aldimines against *F. oxysporum*. Both aldimines and 4-thiazolidinones possessed

Table 2. Characteristics of 4-thiazolidinones of benzal-4-bromoanilines

Compd.	R	M.p. ^a (°C)	Yield (%)	Molecular formula ^b
1b	H	100	58	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ONSBr
2b	4-Cl	140	85	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ONSBrCl
3b	4-OH	185	35	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ NSBr
4b	4-OCH ₃	85	32	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₂ NSBr
5b	3-OCH ₃	105	30	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₃ NSBr
6b	4-OCH ₃	145	40	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₄ NSBr
	3-OCH ₃			
	4-OCH ₃			
7b	3-OCH ₃	87	25	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃ NSBr
	4-OH			
8b	3-OC ₂ H ₅	62	28	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₃ NSBr
	4-OH			

^aThe melting points are uncorrected.

^bThe compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

poor fungitoxicity against *C. capsici*. Three aldimines and four 4-thiazolidinones showed moderate to promising potential against *M. roridum* with one of the 4-thiazolidinones (**8b**) having ED₅₀ value of 170 ppm against this fungus. Only two aldimines and one 4-thiazolidinone indicated ED₅₀ values less than 1000 ppm against *U. tritici*. 3-Ethoxy-4-hydroxybenzal-4-bromoaniline (**8a**) has been found to be the most effective among the test com-

(1a-8a)
Aldimines

(1b-8b)
4-Thiazolidinones

Fig. 1. The reaction sequence.

pounds having ED₅₀ values less than 1000 ppm against all the five test fungi.

Experimental

Synthesis of aldimines of 4-bromoaniline : A mixture of 4-bromoaniline (0.1 mol), benzaldehyde/substituted

Table 3. Fungitoxicity of benzal-4-bromoanilines and their 4-thiazolidinones

Compd.	ED ₅₀ values (ppm) against									
	<i>A. alternata</i>		<i>F. oxysporum</i>		<i>C. capsici</i>		<i>M. roridum</i>		<i>U. tritici</i>	
	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b	a	b
1	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
2	680	850	*	*	*	*	*	390	*	*
3	690	720	*	740	*	790	660	430	410	*
4	570	680	820	770	*	*	*	*	*	*
5	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
6	370	*	*	740	*	*	*	840	*	*
7	700	580	*	*	*	*	670	170	*	870
8	460	720	810	730	740	*	340	*	290	*

*More than 1000 ppm.

a : Aldimines, b : 4-Thiazolidinones.

Note

benzaldehyde (0.1 mol) and methanol (100 ml) was heated for about 5 min in a beaker (250 ml) to get a clear solution. The solution was kept overnight at room temperature to get the respective crude solid which was recrystallized from ethanol to obtain the pure crystals of aldimine **1a-8a** respectively.

Synthesis of 4-thiazolidinones : Benzal-4-bromoaniline or its C-phenyl derivative (**1a-8a**) (0.01 mol) was dissolved in benzene (25 ml) in a conical flask. To the above solution added thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol) and the contents were heated with vigorous shaking. The contents were then cooled and kept overnight when respective crude solid separated out. The solid was filtered and recrystallized from benzene to obtain pure 4-thiazolidinone **1b-8b** respectively.

In vitro screening for fungitoxicity : The stock solutions (2000 ppm) of the aldimines (**1a-8a**) and 4-thiazolidinones (**1b-8b**) were prepared by dissolving each chemical (20 ml) in absolute alcohol (0.5 ml) and the volume was made to 10 ml with sterilized distilled water. Small droplets (0.02 ml) of spore suspension and the compound solution in equal quantity were seeded in cavity

slides. These slides were placed in petriplates lined with moist filter paper and were incubated for 24 h at 25 ± 1 °C. The germination of the spores was recorded and per cent germination inhibition was calculated and ED₅₀ values were determined.

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